

The HuT

Project management plan

Deliverable D7.1

DEVELOPED WITHIN

WP7 Coordination and Management, T7.3 Monitoring and reporting

AUTHORS

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1. Technical references

Project Acronym	The HuT
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Contributing beneficiary/ies	

- * PU = Public
PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)
CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

1.1. Document history

Version	Date	Lead contributor	Description
0.1	28.12.2022	Michele Calvello (UNISA)	First draft
0.2	02.01.2023	Guido Rianna (CMCC)	Critical review and proofreading
1.0	10.01.2023	Michele Calvello (UNISA)	Final version

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3. Management structure

To comply with its objectives, the project needs appropriate management structure and governance.

As such, this deliverable (D7.1) describes the management structure of the The HuT project and the procedures aimed at ensuring the quality of day-to-day project's management and at allowing flexible and rapid responses to situations or challenges.

The Project Management Plan has the following objectives:

- to ensure the correct execution of the project's work plan, including adaptation strategies in case of criticalities that may occur during the project;
- to guarantee efficient communication within the consortium;
- to assure the overall coordination of all activities among the project partners;
- to let the project comply with the objectives, by actively promoting the collaboration of consortium partners and involving relevant external stakeholders;
- to enable timely reporting to the European Commission and the administrative and financial management of the project.

The Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation plan is out of scope of this document, being addressed in deliverable 6.1, to be issued at month 6.

3.1. Roles

The project management plan relies on a hierarchical structure to enable a successful project management and to secure the achievement of the results envisaged by the project.

The organizational structure of the Consortium comprises the Coordinator and four Consortium Bodies.

- The Project Coordinator (PC) is the legal entity acting as the intermediary between the Consortium Partners and the Funding Authority. The Coordinator shall perform the tasks assigned to it as described in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement.
- General Assembly (GA). It is the ultimate decision-making body of the consortium and it is chaired by the Project Coordinator. The GA is composed of one representative of each Consortium Partner.
- Project Management Team (PMT). It is the supervisory body for the execution of the Project which shall report to and be accountable to the General Assembly. It consists of the Coordinator, the deputy-Coordinator, the Project Manager and two WP Leaders. It is responsible and provides oversight for the implementation of the work plan.
- Scientific Coordination Team (SCT). It will assist the Coordinator in the scientific management of the Project. Composition: Coordinator and WP Leaders.
- Demonstrators' arena management board (DMB) Composition: Coordinator, scientific leaders of demonstrators coordinated by WP1 leader.

The HuT project management will thus be carried out at three different levels: 1) strategic, by PMT and GA; 2) scientific, by SCT and DMB; and 3) operational, by WP and Task Leaders.

3.2. Project Coordinator (PC)

The Project Coordinator shall be the intermediary between the Parties and the Funding Authority and shall perform all tasks assigned to it as described in the Grant Agreement and in this Consortium Agreement.

In particular, the PC shall be responsible for:

- monitoring compliance by the Parties with their obligations;
- keeping the address list of Members and other contact persons updated and available;
- collecting, reviewing to verify consistency and submitting reports, other deliverables (including financial statements and related certifications) and specific requested documents to the Funding Authority;
- transmitting documents and information connected with the Project to any other Parties concerned;
- administering the financial contribution of the Funding Authority and fulfilling the financial tasks described in the Consortium Agreement;
- providing, upon request, the Parties with official copies or originals of documents that are in the sole possession of the Coordinator when such copies or originals are necessary for the Parties to present claims.

The HuT PC is Prof. Michele Calvello (UNISA).

3.3. General Assembly (GA)

The General Assembly (GA) is responsible for the decision-making process of The HuT, it is composed of one representative of each Consortium Partner (Table 1) and is chaired by the PC.

The GA will consider and decide appropriately upon any proposed change on the scheduling or structure of the work plan, including changes to consortium plan (e.g., entry/dismal of partners, suspension of all or part of the project) or budget, in accordance with the EU commission. The GA will implement changes to the project in response to recommendations from the boards. The GA is responsible for the proper execution and implementation of the consortium decisions.

Table 1: Representatives of Consortium Partners at General Assembly

ID	Consortium Partner	Representative at GA
1	UNISA	Michele Calvello
2	CMCC	Guido Rianna
2.1	CNR	Valentina Bacciu
3	HEREON	Jo-Ting Huang-Lachmann
4	GFZ	Danijel Schorlemmer
5	IIASA	Joanne Linnerooth-Bayer

ID	Consortium Partner	Representative at GA
6	UPC	Marcel Hurlimann
7	UPV	Manuel Pulido-Velazquez
8	NGI	Luca Piciullo
9	GWP-CEE	Anna Smetanova
10	HY	Sirkku Juhola
11	IMO	Harpa Grímsdóttir
12	VU	Gintautas Stankunavicius
13	ARANTEC	Eisharc Jaquet
14	KOTIVIZIG	György Rátfai
15	ICONS	Ilaria Bonetti
16	LEITHA	Antonio Tirri
17	SOR	Luigi Di Prisco
18	CONF-NO	Francesca Cossu
19	NIP	Ingibjorg Lilja Omarsdottir
20	MA	Tinna Kristbjorg Halldorsdottir
21	UNIGE	Markus Stoffel
22	UCL	Carina Fearnley
23	MET	Joanne Robbins
24	BGS	Katy Freeborough
25	GNDR	Hepi Rahmawati

3.4. Project Management Team (PMT)

The PMT has been appointed by the General Assembly and consists of: Project Coordinator Michele Calvello (UNISA), deputy-Coordinator Guido Rianna (CMCC), Project Manager Alfonso Rossi Filangieri (UNISA), and WP leaders Jo-Ting Huang-Lachmann (HEREON; WP1 leader) and Carina Fearnley (UCL; WP2 leader).

The PMT shall monitor the effective and efficient implementation of the Project. The Coordinator shall chair all the meetings of the PMT, unless decided otherwise by a majority of two-thirds.

In addition, the PMT shall:

- support the PC in preparing meetings with the Funding Authority and in preparing related data and deliverables;
- support the WP6 “Communication, dissemination and exploitation” Leader in preparing the content and timing of press releases and joint publications by the consortium or proposed by the Funding Authority in respect of the procedures of the Grant Agreement Article 17;
- collect information on the progress of the Project, examine that information to assess the compliance of the Project with the Consortium Plan and, if necessary, propose modifications of the Consortium Plan to the General Assembly.

In the case of abolished tasks as a result of a decision of the General Assembly, the PMT shall advise the General Assembly on ways to rearrange tasks of the Parties and where applicable, budgets of the Beneficiaries concerned. Such rearrangement shall take into consideration the legitimate commitments taken prior to the decisions, which cannot be cancelled. If rearranging tasks of Associated Partner(s), the PMT must liaise with the relevant Parties whether the funding from the Associated Partner(s) can be used to cover the rearranged tasks.

3.5. Scientific Coordination Team (SCT)

The Scientific Coordination Team is composed by the PC and all the WP leaders (see Table 3). It shall assist and facilitate the work of the Project Management Team for executing the decisions of the General Assembly as well as the day-to-day management of the Project.

In particular, the SCT will:

- monitor the progress of the project in terms of achievement of objectives and milestones;
- facilitate decision-taking and conflict resolution;
- identify, assess, mitigate, and communicate potential risks and relevant issues during the project life.

3.6. Demonstrators’ arena management board (DMB)

The Demonstrators’ arena management board is composed by the PC and the scientific leaders of the demonstrators coordinated by WP1 leader (Table 2). According to the ANNEX 1 to the Grant Agreement, the DMB will coordinate and supervise the activities carried out in the 10 Demonstrators, making sure that they fulfill what is written in the CA, particularly considering Deliverables and KERs.

Table 2: Identifiers and leaders of Demonstrators (DEM)

DEM #	DEM identifier	Lead participant	DEM Leader
1	Valencia city	UPV	Manuel Pulido Velázquez
2	Val d'Aran region	UPC	Marcel Hürlimann
3	Lattari Mountains	CMCC	Guido Rianna
4	Vilnius city	VU	Gintautas Stankūnavičius

DEM #	DEM identifier	Lead participant	DEM Leader
5	Schleswig-Holstein state and harbour cities	HEREON	Jo-Ting Huang-Lachmann
6	East fjords	IMO	Harpa Grímsdóttir
7	Hungarian Tisza River basin	KOTIVIZIG	György Rátfai
8	Ogliastra province	CMCC	Costantino Battista Sirca
9	Dorset County	BGS	Katy Freeborough
10	Bern canton	UNIGE	Mario Bruno Rohrer

3.7. Work Package Leaders (WP-L)

Work Package Leaders deal with the development tasks and work packages and are responsible for the overall coherence and technical implementation of the project outputs. Each WP-L is responsible for the production of deliverables in the scheduled tasks, allocating the resources, approving the inputs for the WP activities and, finally, collecting contributions to produce the deliverables. The project is divided in 7 Work packages (WPs), as detailed in Table 3.

Table 3: Titles and leaders of Work Packages (WPs)

WP #	WP title	Lead participant	WP Leader
1	Demonstrators' arena	HEREON	Jo-Ting Huang-Lachmann
2	Human behaviours	UCL	Carina Fearnley
3	Governance and policy	IIASA	Joanne Linnerooth-Bayer
4	Science and Technology	CMCC	Guido Rianna
5	Transferability and scalability	GWP-CEE	Anna Smetanova
6	Communication, dissemination and exploitation	ICONS	Ilaria Bonetti
7	Coordination and Management	UNISA	Michele Calvello

3.8. Advisory panels

The project has the following two advisory panels:

- legacy advisory panel (LAP), set to liaise with internationally recognized networks dealing within aligned topics of interest for The HuT with the aim of expanding the boundaries of the consortium during the project and ensuring legacy of the project's innovations;
- legal and ethics advisory panel (LEAP), set to guarantee compliance with ethical and security regulations.

The LAP is composed of the following 5 representatives from internationally recognized networks:

1. Irene Amuron
2. Brian Golding
3. Marleen de Ruiter
4. Manfred Staehli
5. Gavin White

The LEAP is composed of the following three persons who are not members of the consortium:

1. Emilia Garda
2. Jonathan Pratschke
3. Cees van Westen

4. Project structure and timeline

The seven Work Packages of The HuT have been set up to coincide with the main components of the project (Figure 1). The main consortium-wide events, the 14 milestones of the project and the schedule of tasks and deliverables are reported in Figures 2 and 3.

Figure 1: WP tasks and their connections

Figure 2: Main consortium-wide in person events and Milestones

Task	year 1				year 2				year 3				year 4			
1.1				D				D				D				D
1.2				D												
1.3		D														
1.4	D			D				D				D				
1.5					D											
2.1		D														
2.2								D						D		
2.3												D				
2.4																D
3.1										D	D		D			
3.2								D						D		
3.3														D		
4.1		D														
4.2			D							D					D	
4.3			D							D					D	
5.1				DD												
5.2				D				D	D		D	D	D		D	D
5.3															D	
5.4																D
6.1		D											D			
6.2						D				D				D		
6.3								D					D			D
6.4																D
7.1	D															
7.2		D						D						D		
7.3		D														
7.4	D															
7.5	D			D				D					D			D
M		1.2		3	4.5	6		7		8.9	10	11.12			13	14

Figure 3: GANTT chart of milestones (M) and deliverables of the seven work packages (D)

5. Deliverables and submission process

This section is aimed at providing key information about the review process of the deliverables to be released for The HuT. The reviews are aimed at checking the content, the quality, and the coherence of the deliverables. Table 4 reports, for each Deliverable, its typology, the delivery time, the lead contributor, and the partner in charge of the review.

Table 4: List, responsibilities and main features of The HuT deliverables

	Type	Lead Contributor	Delivery at month	Further versions	Reviewer
D1.1 – Ongoing activities in the demonstrators	Synopsis	HEREON	11	23, 25, 47	GWP-CEE
D1.2 – Composition of Local DRR nexus Forums	Report	HEREON	12		GNDR
D1.3 – Architecture of demonstrator’s data portal	Template	NGI	6		GFZ
D1.4 – ‘The Hut for Me and You’	Template	UNIGE	3		UCL
D1.5 – ‘The Hut for Me and You’ narratives	Report	HEREON	12	24, 36	UCL
D1.6 – Standard protocol for evaluating warning systems	Template	MET	14		NIP
D2.1 – SoA on Human-centric DRR activities	Report	UCL	6		HY
D2.2 – Communicating warning messages	Report	UCL	24		KOTIVIZIG
D2.3 – How warnings can be better integrated within society	Policy briefs	UCL	42		GWP-CEE
D2.4 – Co-developing DRR solutions with communities	Report	GNDR	36		UPC
D2.5 – Educational material produced	Report	UPV	36	48	BGS
D3.1 – Innovative policy/governance enablers for multi-risk DRR	Report	UNIGE	32		GNDR
D3.2 – Climate-proofing planning	Guidelines	CMCC	36		IMO

	Type	Lead Contributor	Delivery at month	Further versions	Reviewer
D3.3 – Enablers/barriers of wide-scale implementation of nature-based solutions	Policy brief	IIASA	42		BGS
D3.4 – Quantitative and multi-criteria analyses for multi-risk DRR	Report	HEREON	24		UPV
D3.5 – Serious games for cascading and compound impacts	Manual	GFZ	42		UPV
D3.6 – Prototype of innovative insurance product validated by user groups	Report	CMCC	24		UNISA
D3.7 – Innovative risk transfer and financing for DRR	Report	CMCC	42		UNISA
D4.1 – SoA on prevention and preparedness DRR actions	Report	CMCC	6		ARANTEC
D4.2 – Monitoring activities to be developed in the Demonstrators	Plan	ARANTEC	8		MET
D4.3 – Ongoing monitoring activities in the Demonstrators	Synopsis	ARANTEC	29		VU
D4.4 – The HuT innovative nexus monitoring activities – lessons learned	Report	ARANTEC	44		MET
D4.5 – Modelling activities to be developed in the Demonstrators	Plan	UNISA	9		HEREON
D4.6 – Ongoing modelling activities in the Demonstrators	Synopsis	UNISA	30		UNIGE
D4.7 – The HuT innovative nexus modelling activities – lessons learned	Report	UNISA	44		HEREON
D5.1 – Approaches to transfer DRR innovations	Report	GWP-CEE	12		VU
D5.2 – Documenting DRR solutions and the transfer processes	Template	GWP-CEE	12		KOTIVIZIG

	Type	Lead Contributor	Delivery at month	Further versions	Reviewer
D5.3 – Minutes from I-DRRnF workshops	Report	UNIGE	12	24, 36	NGI
D5.4 – Feedback of Field Visits	Report	GNDR	25	31, 37, 43	ICONS
D5.5 – Replication Roadmap	Report	GWP-CEE	45		UNISA
D5.6 – Scaling up DRR solutions	Policy Brief	HEREON	48		UNISA
D6.1 – Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of results	Plan	ICONS	6	36	IIASA
D6.2 – Outreach and engagement activities	Synopsis	MET	18	30, 42	LEITHA
D6.3 – Networking activities	Synopsis	MET	24	36, 48	UNIGE
D6.4 – Consolidation of the Exploitation Plan	Plan	ICONS	48		IIASA
D7.1 – Project management Plan	Plan	UNISA	3		CMCC
D7.2 – Data management Plan	Plan	UNISA	6	24, 42	ARANTEC
D7.3 – Risk management Plan	Plan	UNISA	6		CMCC
D7.4 – Ethical requirements Plan	Plan	UNISA	3		CMCC
D7.5 – Consortium meetings	Report	UNISA	2	12, 24, 36, 48	CMCC

5.1. Review procedure and scheduling

For a deliverable expected to be released at the end of month x (Mx), the following steps must be followed:

- The **lead contributor** is required to release the first draft at **Mx - 20 days** (suffix to be used “_0.1”)
- The **reviewer** provides feedback and suggestions, complemented by an evaluation sheet (see section 3.2) within 10 days, i.e., before **Mx - 10 days** (suffix to be used “_0.2”)
- The **lead contributor** releases the reviewed version within 7 days, i.e., before **Mx - 3 days** (suffix to be used “_0.3”)

- The **project manager** produced the final PDF and uploads in the EU platform, by the end of **Mx** (suffix to be used “_1.0”)

5.2. Deliverable evaluation sheet

An evaluation sheet, comprising the following 2 tables, will complement the first review.

Table 5: Evaluation sheet - Deliverable format

Item (Answer in 5-point Likert scale: 1=strongly disagree, 5=strongly agree)	Answer	Actions to be undertaken to upgrade the quality of the deliverable before publication
The deliverable follows the agreed template, e.g., The HuT logo in the front page and in the header, the EU logo in the footer, established Font (Helvetica), style of tables		
The deliverable respects the visual identity of the project		
Figures are of adequate quality (proper resolution, readable labels, clear color palette and adequate color selection)		

Table 6: Evaluation sheet - Deliverable content

Item (Answer in 5-point Likert scale: 1=strongly disagree, 5=strongly agree)	Answer	Actions to be undertaken to upgrade the quality of the deliverable before publication
The content corresponds to the deliverable's description indicated in the Grant Agreement.		
Methodology is clearly explained		
The activities and achieved findings are clearly presented and discussed		
The Conclusions well summarize the main aspects covered by the deliverable		

6. Risk Management

The objective of The HuT Risk Management is to provide the process and techniques for the efficient evaluation and control of project risks, focusing on their precautionary diagnoses and effective handling. All The HuT project partners currently operate within an innovative and transformative environment where risk is accepted as a natural consequence of pushing the boundaries of innovation within their respective domains. All The HuT project partners are efficient at horizon scanning and anticipating future risks, as well as identifying, managing and mitigating risks, and as a direct result of their approach to risk, are increasingly resilient to, and recovery quickly from, the impact of risks when they do occur.

The HuT partners consider risk as uncertain events that, upon occurrence, produce negative impact on a project objective/s. The HuT partners readily accept that there are inherent risks related to situations external to the project and risks related to internal project partner problems. Therefore, The HuT risk management strategy will serve to minimise probability and impact for negative risks. In the proposed The HuT risk management methodology, the process involves two activities:

- Risk Management - planning of required activities to manage the risk, evaluation of the results, supported by continuous monitoring and rigorous review.
- Risk Analysis - identification of a risk and assessment of its importance and evaluation of whether it is acceptable for the project.

Risk Management will be performed as an integral part of The HuT Project Management, and the identified risks will be monitored at all PMT monthly meetings throughout the duration of the project. To ensure ownership and oversight of project risk-related processes, The HuT consortium will have responsibility to establish and maintain a The HuT Risk Register, starting from the list of critical risks identified in the Grant Agreement (Table 7), where the probability and impact of all potential identified risks can be assessed, and measures to minimise and mitigate the risks implemented, monitored and reviewed. The HuT Risk Register includes the recording following assessment of the probability and impact of identified risks, measured against a matrix of High, Medium or Low, ranking them in order and establishing appropriate prioritisation and mitigation measures. The 'likelihood' and 'impact' risk level descriptions are as follows.

LIKELIHOOD (L) of risk level descriptions:

1. 'Low' likelihood of risk indicates that the risk is unlikely to occur but requires regular monitoring;
2. 'Medium' likelihood of risk indicates that the risk is likely to occur and requires regular monitoring and review;
3. 'High' likelihood of risk indicates that the risk is highly likely to occur and requires rigorous and regular review.

IMPACT (I) of risk level descriptions:

1. 'Low' impact of risk indicates that the risk will be unlikely to disrupt project progress but requires monitoring. and review;
2. 'Medium' impact of risk indicates that the risk is likely to disrupt project progress and action is required;
3. 'High' impact of risk indicates that the risk is highly likely to disrupt project progress and requires urgent action.

The identification of risks as part of Risk Analysis activity is the responsibility of all The HuT partners. All The HuT partners accept and understand their role and responsibility of continuously horizon scanning for new and emerging risks and reporting any identified risks in line with The HuT Risk Management processes. The identification and reporting of potential risks is an essential role for all project partners to undertake. Any identified potential risk will be immediately reported to The HuT Project Manager who will assess the risks and put in place mitigating measures, monitored via The HuT Risk Register, being underpinned by regular reporting to monthly Project Management meetings and communicated to all project partners.

Table 7: List of critical risks and proposed mitigation measures

#	Description	WP	Mitigation Measures
1	Lack of political commitment from the local authorities in the demonstrators, e.g., due to new elections (L: low, I: high)	WP1, WP3	Engage more with local communities, private sectors, and citizens for bottom-up implementation. Alternatively, find a new Demonstrator in a similar context in the same country to engage and upscale to further regions, and replicate the actions in the original Demonstrator.
2	Pandemic like situation hindering face-to-face stakeholders' engagement and interaction (L: medium, I: low)	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6, WP7	The HuT consortium and demonstrators are all equipped with digital tools for communications. Consortium partners and stakeholders in demonstrators will be provided free access to all the telecommunication software and tools to ensure continuous interactions.
3	Lack of community engagement (L:low, I: high)	WP1, WP2	Work with local leaders and agencies to build trust with local communities and build a collaborative relationship.
4	Unable to engage with vulnerable groups (L: medium, I: low)	WP2, WP6	Work with local community organisations to represent the needs of the vulnerable groups.
5	Language barriers in communication, particularly with the public (L: low, I: medium)	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP5, WP6	The scientific leaders of each demonstrator will be proactive in liaising the English-speaking international partnership with the local language-speaking communities. If needed, local partners will aid the dialogue with the public.
6	Characteristics of extreme climate risk preclude innovative insurance solutions (L: medium, I: low)	WP3	Other innovative financial products, e.g., resilience bonds, will become the focus of this activity.
7	Significant delay in the implementation of IoT monitoring systems (L: medium, I: medium)	WP4	The design and implementation of IoT sensors, by partners with significant expertise on this topic, will explicitly focus on reducing empty times that could negatively impact the deployment of these activities.

#	Description	WP	Mitigation Measures
8	Not enough data in the demonstrators to test and validate models (L: medium, I: medium)	WP4	Exploit freely available datasets, e.g., Copernicus initiatives. Involve local stakeholders to find new useful datasets.
9	Reduced participation in Local/International DRR nexus Forums (L: low, I: high)	WP1, WP5	Involve stakeholders in the demonstrators since the very beginning of the project. Capitalize existing networks of the partners to create links between The HuT and a large audience of potential stakeholders. Encourage stakeholders to take ownership of local Forums' sections.
10	Lack of interest for field visits (L: low, I: medium)	WP5	Clearly communicate the benefits of this action for a proper transfer process. Promote the activity in the Forums.
11	Lack of interest for the HuT activities (L: low, I: high)	WP6	Partners with consolidated expertise in dissemination and communication activities will deploy initiatives to target groups and effectively involve stakeholders.
12	Limited networking activities (L: low, I: high)	WP6	Partners with key positions in established international networks and projects will act to liaise The HuT with these initiatives. A legacy advisory panel will be created.
13	Partner leaving the consortium (L: low, I: medium)	WP7	For each activity, more than one partner is involved. The consortium is formed with redundant skills and responsibilities.
14	Inadequate quality of deliverables or delays in milestones (L: low, I: medium)	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6, WP7	A scientific coordination team, led by the project coordinator, will constantly monitor the progress of the project in terms of achievement of objectives and milestones, and it will ensure the quality and security of the project's outputs.
15	Temporary or permanent absence of personnel caused by sickness or other reasons (L: high, I: low)	WP7	For each activity, more than one partner is involved. The consortium is formed with redundant skills and responsibilities.
16	Key personnel disagreeing on strategic choices and/or on IPR/licensing issues (L: low, I: high)	WP7	All The HuT partners have a long experience in working in international and interdisciplinary teams. Disputes relating to WP tasks are responsibilities of the WP leaders, in consultation with the scientific coordination team. IPR/licensing issues will be dealt with by the project management team.

